

Recommended citation: Yao, W., Chu, Z., & Hu, S. (2019). Global competence of Chinese engineers in Belt and Road initiative - An exploratory study based on grounded theory. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1277-1285). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656702.

Global Competence of Chinese Engineers for the Belt and Road Initiative

--An Exploratory Study based on Grounded Theory

Chu Zhaowei¹

Zhejiang University
Hangzhou City, China

Yao Wei

Zhejiang University
Hangzhou City, China

Hu Shunshun

Zhejiang University
Hangzhou City, China

Conference Key Areas: Talents management; International engineering education

Keywords: BRI Initiative; engineers; global competence;

ABSTRACT

Numbers of qualified Engineers are important guarantee for the successful implementation of BRI (Short for Belt and Road Initiative), and there is still insufficient research on the global competence of Chinese engineers. Several human resources managers from 12 state-owned enterprises were interviewed. These enterprises were developing main businesses along Belt & Road countries. Conversation records (16 hours) were analysed based on grounded theory After a series of abstracted process, these data are organized into three main categories related to global competence with its elements, consequences of lack of that and how to improve it. The study found that the cultural competence, global mindset, adaptability, communication and lifelong learning are the main elements of global competence of engineers. Some implications are proposed, such as universities and colleges in China need to have a global perspective and change their educational concepts. Enterprises should also actively participate in students training, and boldly carry out institutional exploration. Engineers themselves should take the initiative to learn international knowledge, improving their learning ability, and establish the concept of lifelong learning.

¹ Corresponding Author
Chu Zhaowei
chu312@zju.edu.cn

1 INTRODUCTION

The paramount leader of the People's Republic of China, Xi Jinping, originally announced BRI (Short for Belt and Road Initiative) during official visits to Indonesia and Kazakhstan in 2013. The initiative is an effort to improve cooperation and connectivity, to strengthen infrastructure, trade, and investment links between China and other countries [1]. Countries in B&R (short for Belt and Road) area are mainly developing countries (89.06%), most of which are in early stage industrialization and have a huge and urgent need on infrastructure construction. Labor in these countries are featured by unqualified and junior engineers [2]. According to the statistics of Chinese Ministry of Commerce, investment in the B&R region is mainly engineering aspects. In 2017, the turnover of engineering activities of Chinese enterprises in B&R region was US\$168.59 billion, up 5.8% than that in 2016, and the value of newly signed contracts was US\$265.28 billion, increased 8.7% [3]. It is foreseeable that the commercial activities of Chinese enterprises in the B&R countries will further increase the demand for engineers.

In more complicated and unfamiliar investment environment, the investment business in B&R region has brought up new challenges on the global competence of Chinese enterprises and engineers. At present, the research on the global competence of Chinese engineers is still quite scarce. It is necessary to research and help them to improve global competence. Therefore, the research focused on two questions: (1) What are the global competency elements of Chinese engineers? (2) What are the consequences of a lack of global competence for engineers? (3) How to improve the global competence of engineers?

2 REVIEW OF THE GLOBAL COMPETENCE

After McClelland proposed to replace intelligence with competence in test, the word “competence” has been widely used. “Competence” usually referred to “the knowledge, skills, abilities, and traits necessary to enable someone to achieve performance” [4]. The editorial of EJEE (European Journal of Engineering Education) once made a semantic analysis of the word “competence” in engineering education and found that the meaning can be given as knowledge, competence/competencies, ability/abilities, skills, etc., but they believe that the conceptual connotations of these terms are basically consistent [5].

The requirement for global competence of engineers is the result of the globalization of engineering activities. It is obviously significant to clear up the meaning of global competence, as Magleby said: “If this ability is to be taught, developed and assessed, it must first be clearly defined” [6].

At present, researchers have different interpretations of global competence of engineers. Magleby defined 13 dimensions and attributes of global competence. Based on the research of literatures and official documents of several countries, May identified four central global competence related to engineers:

(International)communication, understanding of the engineering profession in a global context, (international) teamwork and ethical reasoning [7]. Patil made a finding to show the significant gap between the expectation of industry to what graduates bring to the work force in global environment [8]. Downey set up a criterion for global competence based on learning outcomes [9]. Most scholars have established their own global competence model for engineering students based on their cultural features and studying environment. Although their interpretations to global competence are so distinct, generally, most of them contain several basic elements such as global awareness, shared values, professionalism, communication.

As for developing global competence, Lohmann summarize several approaches to instil global competence for engineering students such as dual majors, minors and certificates, international experience [10]. Downey classified methods for achieving global competence as five: international enrolment, international project, international work placement, international field trip, integrated class experience [9]. Jesiek introduced a China Research Abroad Program to improve American students' global competence [11].

Compared with the amount of practices and researches on global competence worldwide, there are very few studies on global competency in China [12], due to the current educational system in China is more focused on serving domestic talents needs. At present, there is a general lack of basic theoretical exploration and individual level training practice research, not to mention the special needs for talents in the B&R region. This paper attempts to construct theories for developing Chinese engineering students through grounded theory.

3 .DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Samples and Data

This research is an exploratory study with the aim of theoretical construction, and thus adopts grounded theory. The whole research process includes interview and data collection, coding and theoretical construction. The coding process is divided into initial coding, focused coding and axial coding.

This study fully considered the needs of representativeness and theoretical construction, Interviewees are directors of overseas HR department, overseas business managers or engineers who involved in overseas businesses who are from 12 Chinese state-owned enterprises. Those enterprises have a large volume of business (over 10 billion RMB in turnover), extensive engineering coverage (transportation, construction, energy, communications, etc.) and rich experience in engineering talents management (employees exceeding 1,000) in B&R region.

There are two main ways to collect data: first, interviews, including group interviews, personal interviews, and telephone interviews. Second, examine disclosed information and visit companies and collecting public information. Until it is difficult to

generate new theoretical insights after fresh data collected, it reaches a saturated state and the information collecting will be stopped [13]. In the process of information collecting, this study adopts rolling research, designing open interview outline, and constantly searches for new materials and codes them. When the new coding no longer appears, the data collection process will be stopped and the existing data will be used as a source of data for grounded theoretical research.

Triangular validation method is used to ensure the reliability of data. During the interview process, more than 100,000 (Chinese) words of interview materials were collected and the content was adequate. The coding process was completed by two coders, and the reliability of the encoding is high after calculation. Limited to length, the paper could not offer more details.

3.2 Initial coding

In the Initial coding stage, the interview data was analyzed word by word, and the observed phenomena were “labeled” and the “native code” was retained as much as possible. Finally, 392 initial concepts were formed. Due to space limitations, this article chose a partial encoding as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Examples of Initial coding

typical reference	Initial coding
“... Later, some engineers with good English skills were given priority in promoting, to ensure all of our project managers can communicate without (English) translator.”	Promoting priority
The company's business is mainly based on engineering projects, actively participating in some operations, trade, industrial parks and free trade zone investment and estate development, to help the local economic developing fully. At the same time, we are trying to achieve business transformation and diversification.”	Business Diversification
"Some engineering students can come to a country as a director (project management) in two or three years. Students, who ranked top in grades but lack comprehensive abilities, are often eliminated. Some time ago, we just eliminated a undergraduate form Tsinghua University.	Requirements for comprehensive abilities
...	

Source: According to the interview data.

3.3 Focused coding

In the focused coding, the initial concepts are continued to be summarized and refined, and the same initial concepts are integrated to 60 initial categories. Based on the initial categories that have been extracted, this paper attempts to use the classical paradigm “Casual Condition-Phenomenon-Context-Intervening Condition-Action/Interaction-Consequence” proposed by Glaser to link these concepts [14]. Table 2 takes the two paradigms of causal conditions and intervening condition as examples, and illustrates the all the initial categories.

Table 2 Initial categories using typical paradigm combinations

Paradigm	Amount	Concrete Initial Categories
Causal Condition	8	lack of engineering practice in school; evaluation system based on grades; rigid choice system; company's business shifts from home to abroad; company's business diversification; company's business upgrading; high cost of employment; hiring local worker;
Intervening condition	12	engineering leadership; teamwork ability; English communication skills; non-universal language learning and application; engineering investment management; operational management; risk management; cross-cultural leadership; communication with local community; limited promoting ways; rigid incentive system;

3.4 Axial coding

In the axial coding phase, it is mainly to combine similar initial categories. As shown in Table 3, in the analysis of “causal conditions”, it is easy to find that three initial categories: insufficient engineering practice training in university; Score-oriented evaluation system; rigid talents selection system, have similar meaning and can be reduced to the main category “defect of talents training”. Some initial categories are related to the company's strategic options. such as: business shifts from home to abroad; business diversification; business upgrading, which can be reduced to main category “Company business transformation”. Other initial categories can be reduced in the same way.

after the collections of initial categories are gradually abstracted one by one, all the concept categories are organized into three main categories finally. These main categories are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Main categories using typical categories

Paradigm	Insufficient global	Talents structure	Engineering human

	competence	contradiction	resources improvement
Causal conditions	Deficient talents training	Company business transformation	High cost for company
Phenomenon	Narrow skill for engineers	Talents structural mismatch	Weak capability of work adaptability and job rotation
Context	Cross-cultural engineering environment	Cross-cultural business environment	Fierce business competition
Intervening condition	Frequent communication and collaboration in engineering field	Comprehensive business capabilities	Insufficient incentives mechanism
Action/ Interaction	Enhance employees' global competence	human resources structure Improvement	Training and incentives Improvement
consequence	Restricted business operation	Multiple Restrict on development	Exploration on human resources management

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 The lack of global competence and its impact

According to the above three core categories in Table 3, we can sort out related issues from three aspects and understand the global competence of engineers.

First of all, the talents selection for international business, Chinese companies find that engineers are obviously lacking of comprehensive quality and global competence. These weaknesses are further magnified in frequent communication and collaboration with foreign officials, engineers, and communities when they were undertaking engineering project in transnational and cross-cultural environment. As a result, companies have to spend a lot of time and money, starting from talents selection and internal training to improve that. The lack of global competence has led directly to constraints the business development of the company.

Secondly, in developing overseas business, Chinese engineering companies generally develop core international business first, and then gradually diversify according to the core business, then transform and upgrade it. When human resources mismatched with company's requirements, the phenomenon of talents structural imbalance will appear. This phenomenon could be mainly manifested in "two contradictions": abundant engineers who are capable of profession but scarce

engineers who are capable of management and international business activities; sufficient basic engineer but deficient top talents. In the transnational and cross-cultural business environment, the development of business activities focusing on engineering construction poses a comprehensive challenge to the business ability (or non-technology ability) of engineering talents. Enterprises try to improve the talent structure through process optimization on personnel recruitment, internal selection and targeted training etc. A series of problems caused by the structural contradiction of talents make the development of enterprises face many constraints, such as capital shortage, risk increasing and business upgrading hindering.

Finally, when undertaking international business, local employment will bring challenges to the risk of cost and management. However, Off-site work strategy also has some defects, such as poor rotation ability, inadaptable work and insufficient skills of domestic employees, so enterprises are in a dilemma of "talents shortage". Furthermore, under the constraints of the incentive system, employees lack the motivation to self-improvement. In response to this situation, one thing the company only can do is to actively improve the training and incentives for employees, and to some extent, to achieve a "breakthrough" of the inherent system.

4.2 Global competency and its elements

Through the above analysis, a global competence model has been built in Fig. 1. It can be found that in this model the global competency of the B&R engineers generally has the following five capabilities. Firstly, cultural competence. It is the ability to understand and respect local culture and values. Actively understanding the religious beliefs, customs, cultural traditions and values of the territories is significant.

Fig. 1. Global competence model

Secondly, Global mindset. It means global vision, global knowledge and global thinking. In the B&R project, we need to consider and organize engineering activities

from the perspective of globalization, and maintaining a good cooperation relationship. Thirdly, Adaptability. It is the ability to actively integrate into local culture and society. Engineers are not only "builders", but also "national cards" and "cultural messengers". They must be able to maintain relationships, shape a good national and organizational image and create a well investment environment. Fourthly, Communication. It is the ability to compete daily and professional communication. Finally, Lifelong learning. It means strong learning motivation and ability. Engineers must have self-improved learning awareness and learning ability as a guarantee to continuously improve their abilities.

5 IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

Considering a lot of defects mentioned above in talents training, we proposed some suggestions to improve this. First and foremost, it is urgent to change the educational goal. At present, the goal of Chinese education system is only focus on fulfilling the needs of domestic industry development and overlooks consideration of international demand, thus led to inadequate global competence. As Teng said, what Chinese students need most now is systematic global competency education rather than a kind of knowledge or ability. Propelling the school-enterprise cooperation in students training will be a considerable way, by forming a whole training-chain of "school training, internship program in school, and internship in enterprises". It worth noting that Chinese universities should strengthen cooperation between them and multinational companies, and encourage or help their engineering students to practice or work in a real international background.

For companies, they should try to hire more local employees. Whether it is economic or legal, that will be beneficial for company's long-term development. However, they should actively promote the two-way flow of engineers in the company, to improve engineers' global competence, and enable engineers to be qualified for international background in language, values and emotions. In addition, the company should provide more exchanges, cooperation and even mobility opportunities for employees in different jobs to enhance their cooperation. Also, while they are expanding their engineering experience, it is time to help them to be a project manager gradually.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Bank. Belt and Road Initiative[EB/OL]. <http://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/regional-integration/brief/belt-and-road-initiative>.2018-03-29/2019-04-15.
- [2] Jian LIN. Dexin HU. "One belt one road" National Strategy and the New Mission of Chinese Engineering Education[J]. HIGHER ENGINEERING EDUCATION,2016(6):3-3.(In Chinese)
- [3] Shengwen WANG. Report on the development of China's foreign contracted projects(2017-2018) [R]. BeiJing: Ministry of Commerce of the People's Republic

of China,2018.

- [4] Mcclelland DC. Testing for Competence Rather Than Intelligence[J]. American Psychologist, 1973, 28(1):1-14.
- [5] Lemaitre D, PratRL, GraaffED,et al. Editorial:Focusing on competence[J].European Journal of Engineering Education, 2006, 31(1):45-53.
- [6] Magleby SP, Harb JN, Parkinson AR.Developing Global Competence in Engineers: What Does it Mean? What is Most Important?[C].Asee Conference and Exposition.2009.
- [7] May D, TekkayaE. The Globally Competent Engineer–What Different Stakeholders Say About Educating Engineers for a Globalized World[C]// International Conference on Interactive Collaborative Learning. IEEE, 2015:924-930.
- [8] Patil C.S. Nair Codner G. Global accreditation for the global engineering attributes: A way forward. In:Proceedings of the 2008 AaeE Conference. 2008
- [9] Downey GL, LucenaJC, MoskalBM,etal. The Globally Competent Engineer: Working Effectively with People Who Define Problems Differently[J].Journal of Engineering Education,2006, 95(2):107–122.
- [10]Lohmann JR,RollinsHA,HoeyJJ.Defining,developing and assessing global competence in engineers[J].European Journal of Engineering Education,2006,31(1):119-131.
- [11]Jesiek B K, Haller Y, Thompson J. Developing Globally Competent Engineering Researchers: Outcomes-Based Instructional and Assessment Strategies from the IREE 2010 China Research Abroad Program[J]. Advances in Engineering Education, 2014, 4(1).
- [12]Teng Jun , Zhang Tingting& Hu Jiayi.Preparing Students with "Global Competence" - The New Idea of American International Education and Its Critical Reflection in China[J].Educational Research,2018(1).(In Chinese)
- [13]K·Charmaz. Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis [M].SAGE,2006:144-147.
- [14]Glaser BG, Strauss AL.The Discovery of Grounded Theory:Strategies for Qualitative Research[M].New York:Aldine Publishing Company,1967.